

RINAsense: A prototype for implementing RINA networks in IoT environments

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Abstract—The Internet of Things (IoT) enables several services and applications for improving human beings' quality of life. Nowadays, several IoT devices have been deployed in multiple domain applications, and remarkable growth is expected in the coming years. This high adoption of IoT solutions brings about complex network management, technological fragmentation, and security costs. The Recursive Inter-Networking Architecture (RINA) has recently emerged as a future Internet paradigm to overcome network complexity. RINA has shown relevant advantages in security, management, and performance by minimizing the number of protocols to only two and extracting as much commonality as possible. However, RINA has not been tested in IoT environments due to the lack of a RINA implementation for embedded devices. For this reason, this paper presents the RINAsense implementation for embedded devices to facilitate RINA prototyping in IoT environments. An instance of RINAsense was implemented by using the ESP32 IoT platform and the FreeRTOS kernel. The instance used Wi-Fi technology to communicate with an IRATI-based IoT gateway. RINAsense components were developed as a set of libraries based on the C language to facilitate the replicability and extension of the implementation. Finally, a testbed was implemented to measure RINAsense performance regarding goodput, packet loss, and delay. RINAsense implementation achieved a goodput of 1,18 Mbps, 0,01% packet loss, and an average of 2,3 milliseconds delay.

Index Terms—IoT, RINA, Future Networks, Network Architecture, Network Protocol

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) has the potential to change human beings' daily activities and enhance human beings' quality of life. Nowadays, massive IoT devices are being deployed in several IoT ecosystems. For instance, almost 12.2 billion IoT devices are growing up actively connected to the Internet [1]. Also, IoT has unleashed a promised business value. Indeed, the IoT market grew 22,4% in 2021 and is expected to grow 24% in the coming years [2]. Thus, IoT technologies enable scenarios in which things interact with us anywhere and anytime.

However, IoT faces new challenges, such as complex network management, increasing security costs, and technological fragmentation. The IoT heterogeneity increases the complexity of the IoT environment. IoT has a wide range of applications protocols (CoAP, MQTT, among others) and technologies (Wireless-Fidelity (Wi-Fi), Bluetooth, Zigbee, among others) that are increasing the complexity of managing the network

and the IoT device inventory [3]. Also, bringing security to IoT environments implies adding expensive security equipment. Indeed, security is one of the most relevant problems derived from the TCP/IP stack, which was created without security levels [4]. Finally, IoT heterogeneous is leading a technological fragmentation that is creating barriers and locking in customers. The industry is more dedicated to overcoming these barriers to entry instead of building high-quality services [5]. The current IoT adoption leads to complex, high-cost, and inefficient systems.

The Recursive Inter-Networking Architecture (RINA) emerges as a network paradigm to overcome the current Internet protocol chaos and reduce its complexity [6]. RINA is based on the idea that a computer network is itself a distributed application that provides distributed Inter-Process Communication (IPC) services to other distributed applications [7]. The architecture is based on a single type of layer known as Distributed Inter-Process Communication Facility (DIF). The network designer can repeat as many DIFs as required. This recurrence is the most essential aspect of the RINA. Moreover, RINA provides as much invariance as possible by extracting as much commonality (patterns) as possible without creating exceptional cases [6]. In other words, RINA separates transfer mechanisms (invariance) and policies (patterns). This separation facilitates network customization and operation, avoiding redundant mechanisms implementation.

RINA has demonstrated several advantages compared to current network architectures. RINA provides two protocols for data transfer and management protocols. This simplification reduces the network complexity in comparison to TCP/IP stack [8] [9]. Also, RINA's security approach has been analyzed and tested in the PRISTINE project, demonstrating the security benefits of protecting a complete layer instead of individual protocols [10]. RINA minimizes security costs and provides flexibility and reusability of security policies [11].

Currently, there are several software-based implementations of RINA architecture, such as IRATI [12], rlite [13], and Pro-RINA [14], for quick prototyping in academic environments. Also, there is a RINA simulator for an easy understanding of RINA concepts and rapidly prototyping [15]. The Academic works have discussed the potential benefits of RINA in IoT environments [16] [17]. However, the lack of a RINA implementation for embedded devices has reduced the possibility

of enabling testbeds and IoT devices for testing RINA in IoT environments.

This paper presents the RINAsense architecture for facilitating the implementation of RINA-based sensors and the adoption of RINA in IoT environments. We have implemented an instance of the RINAsense architecture using an ESP32 SoC IoT platform and relying on the FreeRTOS kernel as the real-time operating system. This RINA-based sensor prototype used Wi-Fi technology to communicate to a RINA-based IoT gateway implemented using IRATI open source. Moreover, we have developed the RINA components as a set of libraries based on C language to facilitate the replicability and extension of the implementation. Finally, we have tested the performance of the RINA-based sensor in terms of goodput, packet loss, and delay. We have analyzed the protocol efficiency in comparison to the current TCP/IP stack protocol.

This paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the RINA approach, concept, and protocol review. Section III describes the RINAsense architecture and details its components. Section IV presents the RINAsense implementation details. Section V explains the experiment scenario and the evaluation of the RINA-based prototype. Finally, Section VI presents our conclusions and future improvements.

II. RINA APPROACH

RINA is based on a single layer known as DIF. A DIF comprises several IPC processes (IPCPs) that cooperate in providing IPC services to applications or upper DIFs. The network designer can repeat as many DIFs as required to cover the network scope (e.g., a LAN, a campus Network, a WAN, or an ISP network). This recurrence is an essential aspect of RINA networks [6].

Fig. 1. Generic RINA network approach.

There are two types of DIFs: shim DIFs and Normal DIFs, as Figure 1 shows.

- Shim DIFs are adaptations of existing protocols. The shim DIF wraps the underlying protocol layer with the IPC service interface. The IPCPs that are part of a shim DIF are called shim IPCPs. Since the shim DIF depends on the underlying protocol, it should provide no more service or capability than the legacy protocol. There are some shim DIFs already developed to overlay RINA on top of

network technologies such as Wi-Fi [12], VLAN [18], and TCP/UDP [8].

- Normal DIFs provide the exact fixed mechanisms such as data transfer, data transfer control, routing, access control, and service data unit (SDU) protection, among others. A normal DIF uses the services of underlying DIFs (shims or normal) to transfer data across the network.

DIF functionalities follow the principle of separation of mechanism from the policy. As a result, DIF functionalities are programmed using policies without implementing dedicated protocols. The two generic protocols in a DIF are the Error Flow Control Protocol (EFCP) and the Common Distributed Application Protocol (CDAP).

EFCP provides a single data transport protocol framework. EFCP has two parts: (i) Data Transfer Protocol (DTP) and (ii) Data Transfer Control Protocol (DTCP). The DTP implements tightly coupled mechanisms to data transfer PDUs, such as flow addressing or sequencing. Meanwhile, the DTCP implements loosely coupled mechanisms, such as flow control or retransmission control. DTCP functionality is based on Delta-t protocol [19], and DTCP processes control PDUs. EFCP creates one or more data transfer PDUs and hands them over the Relaying and Multiplexing Task (RMT). The RMT is responsible for forwarding decisions to transfer data using N-1 DIF.

CDAP operates on remote objects used by all the layer management functions. CDAP unifies sharing data over the network [6]. The different layer management functions of an IPCP leverage a common machinery to exchange information with its peers. To do so, the Resource Information Base (RIB) stores the IPCP state as objects. The RIB objects model includes the object naming, relationships between objects (inheritance, containment, among others), the object attributes, and the CDAP operations that can be applied to them [6]. The RIB Daemon manages access to the RIB and exchanges CDAP PDUs with RIB Daemons of neighbor IPCPs. The only operations that can be performed on objects are: create/delete, read/write and start/stop. The RIB Daemon implements the Common Application Connection Establishment Phase (CA-CEP), which exchanges naming information with peers. CDAP helps implement layer management functionalities such as enrollment, flow allocation, and routing.

- Enrollment: is the procedure by which an IPCP joins an existing DIF and is initialized with enough information to become a fully operational DIF member [6]. This procedure starts after an application connection is established. The enrollment is specific for each DIF and can be configured using a policy. The RIB updates its objects once the new IPCP joined to the DIF.
- Flow Allocation: is responsible for creating and managing flows. The application process above the DIF requests a flow using the well-defined IPC service API. The flow allocator creates a dedicated flow allocator instance (FAI) to manage the flow life-cycle. The FAI determines the flow characteristics based on policies. The FAI creates

Fig. 2. RINAsense High-Level Layered Architecture.

the EFCP instance for the requested flow before sending the CDAP Create Flow Request to find the destination application and determine whether the requestor has access to it [6].

- **Routing:** is responsible for creating a forwarding function using RIB information. The routing algorithms are set by using a policy [6].

III. RINAsense ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

The proposed RINAsense architecture is organized in layers. It comprises four layers: data link, operating system (OS) and Abstraction, RINA, and application layer. Figure 2 shows the layered high-level RINA sensor architecture.

- **Data Link Layer:** oversees moving data into and out of a wireless link in a network. It comprises wireless technologies used in IoT environments. It provides services to the above DIFs to move data between sensors or through a RINA-based IoT gateway to edge nodes or the cloud. So, it is necessary to implement a shim IPCP for each wireless technology.
- **RINA Layer:** provides all RINA components to implement a system with RINA networking capabilities. This layer provides functionalities for transmitting data, controlling the data transmission, and managing the RINA network. The RMT, EFCP, IPCP, and shim IPCP modules provide functionalities for data transmission, such as SDUs multiplexing, splitting SDUs, or flow data control. Meanwhile, the resource allocator, enrollment task, flow allocator (FA), namespace manager, RIB, and routing modules provide functionalities to manage tasks such as specific routing algorithms, quality of service, flow priorities, names and address management, or allocating and deallocating flows. All RINA components are implemented following their definitions published in [6].
- **Application Layer:** delivers applications or services to sense the environment(sensors) and make some response (actuators). These applications and services can be deployed in many environments, such as home, agriculture, health, transport, and industry, enabling smart environments.
- **OS and Abstraction Layer:** provides a runtime environment to controlling the functionalities of the previ-

ous layers. These tasks share a single processing core using the Free Real Time Operating System (FreeRTOS). This layer relies on FreeRTOS because of its extension portability over several microcontroller platforms. Also, it provides hardware abstraction for controlling not only the data link technologies drivers but also the microcontroller platform hardware components such as the Real-time Clock (RTC), embedded flash, peripheral interfaces based on Inter-Integrated Circuit (i2C), or the Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter (UART). In addition, this layer provides a portability sublayer to allow writing cross-platform software to control devices based on the IoT development framework for ESP32 (ESP-IDF), Arduino, or Linux.

IV. RINAsense PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

An instance of the RINAsense architecture was implemented to test the feasibility of the RINA networks in IoT applications. This first RINA prototype was focused on using Wi-Fi technology in the Data Link layer. Wi-Fi technology is widely used in IoT environments, making it easy to prototype and test. We employed an ESP32-WROOM-32 to implement the prototype following the context of the TERMINET project. The ESP32 is a low-cost chip microcontroller (SoC) system that integrates Wi-Fi and dual-mode Bluetooth. The ESP32-WROOM-32 has a Tensilica Xtensa dual-core 32-bits LX6 microprocessor, 320 KiB RAM, and 4MiB flash memory. In addition, we employed the official IoT development framework for ESP32 (ESP-IDF), which is open-source and facilitates the development of any generic application¹. Also, we employed the FreeRTOS kernel provided by the ESP-IDF, which is modified for multicore support, as an RTOS kernel for implementing the OS and abstraction layer. Consequently, the RINAsense prototype followed the ESP-IDF development application model. The RINAsense implementation is available as open-source in a github repository².

The RINAsense prototype has three parts: (i) the shim IPCP, (ii) the normal IPCP, and (iii) the RINA sense core. Figure 3. shows the modules implemented in the RINAsense prototype and how they interact.

A. RINAsense core

The RINAsense core comprises the RINA task, RINA API, ids manager, RINA timers, and the RINA buffer manager. The RINA task is the core of the RINAsense implementation and has the highest priority to run. The RINA task follows an event model. All components connected to the RINA task, as shown in Figure 3, send events to the RINA task. It manages and executes the corresponding functionalities of the Normal IPCP, shim IPCP, and RINA API. The RINA task relies on the IDs manager to control the CEP-Ids and IPCP Port-Ids assigned to the Normal IPCP, shim IPCP, and the application process. Also, the RINA task depends on the RINA timers to execute repetitive activities, such as

¹<https://docs.espressif.com/projects/esp-idf/en/latest/esp32/index.html>

²<https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/rinasense>

Fig. 3. RINAsense Stack.

updating the ARP cache and scheduling the RMT queue. The RINA timers are an abstraction of FreeRTOS timers to start, reload, and stop timers. The RINA buffer manager oversees the network’s buffer life-cycle (initializing, getting, and releasing network buffers) in the RINAsense prototype. The RINA API provides interfaces to the application process for allocating flows (`RINA_alloc_flow()`), deallocating flows (`RINA_dealloc_flow()`), writing (`RINA_write(portId)`), and reading SDUs (`RINA_read(portId)`) from the flows. By doing so, an application process can request to allocate a flow, and if the flow is successfully allocated, the application process will write or read SDU to/from the flow.

B. NORMAL IPCP

The normal IPCP implements the essential RINA modules in its first version. The normal IPCP comprises the RMT, EFCP, RIB, RIB Daemon, enrollment task, and flow allocator. These modules facilitate the implementation of the standard DIF functionalities to transfer data and manage tasks.

The functionality to transfer data is implemented using the RMT and EFCP IPCP modules. The IPCP creates an EFCP container to support multiple EFCPs. This scenario helps support more than one application process. The EFCP instance is created inside the EFCP container when the FA handles the flow allocation request. This instance is composed of a DTP and DTCP. We just implemented the DTP in this first version, so the implementation supports only unreliable

flows. The EFCP container keeps a list of EFCP created and its connections’ end-points identifier(CepId). Also, the EFCP container exposes API for creating, modifying, updating, and deleting connections. The FAI uses this API to manage the flow life cycle. Once a flow has been allocated, the EFCP is ready to receive data from the application process through the `RINA_write()` API.

The RMT makes forwarding decisions on incoming PDUs and multiplexes multiple flows of outgoing PDUs onto one or more (N-1) flows. There is one RMT per IPCP. The RMT has a FIFO queue for each N-1 DIF, which is associated with the N-1 portId. If the N-1 DIF is busy, the RMT will enqueue SDUs and schedule a dequeued based on a policy. The scheduler uses a RINA timer defined by policy to execute the dequeue.

This first version implements the enrollment task and flow allocation management layer functionalities. The enrollment task is employed for the CACEP and exchanging naming information. It is called from the RINA task after the IPCP modules have been initialized. This task relies on RIB Daemon for the CACEP. The first CACEP stage is to create a `M_CONNECT` CDAP message with source and destination information (application process name and application process instance) and authentication policy (optional). If the authentication policy is defined, the IPCPs will exchange authentication information. After CACEP was established, the IPCPs exchanged `M_START` and `M_START_R` CDAP messages with their address information. Also, the IPCPs exchange `M_CREATE` with the enroller neighbor information to be stored as a neighbor object into the RIB. Once this procedure is completed successfully, the IPCP is ready to provide services to the application process.

The flow allocation functionality is employed for handling application processes’ flow allocating requests. The application process requests a flow by using the `RINA_flow_alloc()` API, and it is blocked for waiting for the response. It creates a new FAI and sends a `M_CREATE` CDAP message to trigger a remote flow allocation in the remote IPCP. Once the remote IPCP confirms the legit of the request by using a `M_CREATE_R`, the FAI changes the flow port Id state to `FLOW_ALLOCATED_STATUS` and notifies to the application process. The application process uses the port Id to inject data into the flow by calling the `RINA_write(portID)`.

C. SHIM IPCP

The shim IPCP is an adaptation of the Wi-Fi to a DIF (shim DIF) and allows the DIF above built using the IPC service API to operate over Wi-Fi. We have implemented the ARP, Shim Wi-Fi, and Wi-Fi driver interface modules to enable the shim IPCP. The ARP module is a lightweight implementation of the RFC 826, adapted from the ARP826 module of the IRATI open-source project [12]. The ARP module will update the ARP cache constantly so that the RINAsense will send and receive ARP requests and replies. The Wi-Fi Driver interface module abstracts the ESP32 driver’s Wi-Fi functionalities allowing it to take control of the ESP32 Wi-Fi driver. The

primary Wi-Fi Driver interface functionalities are initializing the ESP32 Wi-Fi driver as an access point (AP) or a station mode and managing incoming and outgoing packets.

The Shim Wi-Fi module implements the standard DIF functionalities such as enroll to DIF, flow allocation request, flow allocation response, flow deallocate, application register, application unregister, and SDU write. The enrollment to DIF functionality allows for initializing the ESP32 Wi-Fi driver and associating it with the remote AP. Once the enrollment is completed, the DIF above uses the application register functionality to be registering. Then, the ARP module structures an ARP reply packet in a network buffer with the application name of the DIF above as a general address protocol and sends the network buffer to the ESP32 Wi-Fi driver to be broadcasted. Then, the remote device sends an ARP response as described in RFC 826. Next, the DIF above creates a flow allocation request and waits until the remote IPCP responds to the flow allocation. Once the flow is allocated, the DIF above is available to write DUs into the flow by using the DU write functionality of the shim DIF. Also, the shim Wi-Fi module implements ethernet frame processing functionality to evaluate whether a packet entered into the ESP32 Wi-Fi Driver buffer is a RINA or ARP packet. If the packet is a RINA packet, the packet will be sent to the DIF above. Meanwhile, if the packet is an ARP packet, the packet will be sent to the ARP module.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We designed a testbed to measure the performance of the RINA-based sensor. This testbed consists of two hosts: (i) a RINA-based sensor implemented using the ESP32 development platform and (ii) an IRATI-based IoT gateway implemented using a Raspberry Pi v3 with Raspbian Stretch S.O., and the IRATI open-source software [12]. The scenario aims to evaluate the functionality of the shim IPC process for WiFi and verify the normal DIF capacities to support enrollment tasks, allocate unreliable flows, and transmit data. Figure 4. shows the scenario to be tested. We designed several experiments based on this scenario to measure the goodput, loss packets, delay, and protocol efficiency.

Fig. 4. Scenario for experiments.

A. Goodput and Packet Loss

We used one instance of the rinaperf application as an application process running on server mode in the IRATI-based IoT gateway. This application is part of the IRATI open source and provides several tools to measure goodput and round-time transmission (RTT) between two IRATI-based nodes. Since the rinaperf application was not developed considering the resources limitations nor embedded programming models, we developed an application to act as a rinaperf client in the RINA-based sensor. This rinaperf client followed the task-based programming model to exploit the RINA layer APIs and interact with the remote rinaperf server application and measure the goodput and delay.

The rinaperf client application allocated two flows with the rinaperf server. The first flow aimed to send control information, while the second aimed to send data information. This application employs as parameters the number of SDUs to send, the SDU size in bytes, and the test time interval during which the goodput was measured. Once the control flow between the RINA-based sensor and the RINA-IoT Gateway was allocated, the application sent the test parameters to the rinaperf server. The rinaperf server responded by adding a test ticket number. Then, the test ticket number was sent as the first message in the data flow to indicate to the rinaperf server which data flow was related to the flow control. Next, the rinaperf client injected the SDUs into the data flow using the RINA write API. At the end of the test, the rinaperf server sent a message including the test results (number of packets received, the packets per second average, and the goodput average in Mbps).

Fig. 5. Application Goodput in function of SDU size.

We performed seven tests using 2000 SDUs of 7 different sizes (32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 1480 Bytes) for 10 seconds. Figure 4 shows the goodput obtained during the test, and it is compared with the theory goodput. The theory goodput refers to the maximum goodput that the instance of the proposed architecture can reach using the ESP32 under ideal conditions (changing some ESP32 components parameters, but it is not

recommendable due to aggressive resource consumption that can cause application malfunction). The maximum goodput achieved by the implementation is 1,18 Mbps sending a packet with 1480 SDU size. The goodput curve is considered acceptable for IoT sensor applications which usually send data with low data rate [20].

The packet loss is another interesting parameter to evaluate networks. We evaluated packet loss by varying ESP32 WiFi driver buffers in this case. The ESP32 WiFi driver buffers share the memory with the application, so a more significant number of WiFi driver buffers allocated less memory for the application. The memory is restricted in IoT SoC platforms, and we must use it properly. We experimented with 4, 8, and more than 16 buffers to understand how the memory affected packet loss. We performed the same test as the goodput by sending 2000 packets in 10 seconds and counting the number of packets the rinaperf server received. Table 1 shows the average packet loss for different SDUs sizes (32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 1480) for each type of buffer allocation scheme, static or dynamic. The results show it is necessary to use only 16 buffers to achieve a packet loss of 0,01 %. Also, the goodput did not experiment with any change when using 16, 32, or 64 buffers. Thus, if more than 16 buffers are used, it wastes unnecessary memory resources because neither the packet loss nor the goodput will be improved.

TABLE I
PACKET LOSS PERCENTAGE RESULTS

# Buffers Driver WiFi	4	8	>16
Buffer Static Allocation	60,97%	17,46%	0,01%
Buffer Dynamic Allocation	63,77%	16,65%	0,01%

B. Delay

We developed another application to measure RTT. Like the rinaperf client application, this second application (rinaping) allocated a control and data flow. This application uses the SDU size in bytes and the number of SDUs sent as parameters. Once the flow was allocated, the application sent an SDU to the rinaperf server, activated a timer, and waited for the response for 2 seconds. On the other side, the rinaperf server returned the SDU as soon as possible. When the rinaping read the SDU using the `RINA_read()` API, it stopped the timer, calculated the RTT, and stored the RTT. This process is repeated as many SDUs numbers were configured in the application. We repeated all processes changing the SDUs size (32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024 Bytes). At the end of the test, the rinaping application showed the final statistics RTT (minimum, maximum, and average). We observed that the communication delay is around 2.3 milliseconds on average, and the SDUs size is not affecting this delay. The maximum RTT is 5.4 milliseconds, and the minimum is 1.2 milliseconds. This RTT is considered very acceptable in WiFi connections. IoT applications usually require a delay of fewer than 10 milliseconds, according to the IEEE Standard 2413-2019 for IoT [21].

C. Protocol Efficiency

The protocol efficiency tends to evaluate the performance of the transport protocol to transfer data between nodes. Each transport protocol adds protocol headers to facilitate the data transfer. However, when the header size is more significant than the data size, it is less efficient, affecting the goodput directly. We calculated the protocol efficiency ratio by making a relationship between the data size and the message size (data size + headers size). For this analysis, we used two well-known IoT application protocols (MQTT and CoAP) and compared when these protocols are used with the TCP/IP stack and the RINA EFCP protocol. We consider the header size for TCP/IP as 40 Bytes and UDP/IP 28 Bytes, while the RINA EFCP header size is 14 Bytes. Figure 6 shows the protocol efficiency ratio comparison. The EFCP protocol achieved more efficiency than the TCP/IP stack because its header is less than TCP/IP stack. The efficiency is more notorious when we transfer messages with a small size (less than 300 Bytes). Meanwhile, the efficiency is similar when we transfer messages with large sizes (more than 1000 Bytes). Since IoT usually transfer small message, the EFCP protocol is more efficient for IoT applications than the TCP/IP stack.

Fig. 6. Protocol Efficiency Ratio in function of Message Size.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the RINAsense architecture for embedded devices to overcome the lack of a RINA stack implementation for resource-constrained devices. A RINAsense instance was implemented using the ESP32 IoT platform and the FreeRTOS kernel. The implementation performance was tested using an IRATI-based IoT gateway. The experimental tests showed that RINAsense implementation provides high goodput, low delay, and packet loss for supporting the development of IoT services and applications. Also, we have demonstrated that RINA improves protocol efficiency in IoT environments by comparing the RINA stack and TCP/IP stack. The RINAsense implementation has demonstrated the applicability of RINA in IoT environments, but its performance can still be improved. As future improvements, the rest of the RINA

components will be implemented to enable a fully RINA-based prototype for extending the experimental environment. Also, RINAsense will be extended to support other wireless technologies, such as Bluetooth, and ZigBee, among others, and to be easily portable to other IoT development platforms.

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REFERENCES

- [1] IoT Analytics, "State of IoT 2022: Number of connected IoT devices growing 18% to 14.4 billion globally." <https://iot-analytics.com/number-connected-iot-devices/>. Accessed: 2022-09-30.
- [2] IoT Analytics, "Global IoT market size grew 22% in 2021 — these 16 factors affect the growth trajectory to 2027." <https://iot-analytics.com/iot-market-size/>. Accessed: 2022-09-30.
- [3] S. T. Arzo, C. Naiga, F. Granelli, R. Bassoli, M. Devetsikiotis, and F. H. P. Fitzek, "A Theoretical Discussion and Survey of Network Automation for IoT: Challenges and Opportunity," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 15, pp. 12021–12045, 2021.
- [4] N. B. Samyuel and B. A. Shimray, "Securing iot device communication against network flow attacks with recursive internetworking architecture (rina)," *ICT Express*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 110–114, 2021.
- [5] M. Rizinski, J. Day, and L. Chitkushev, "Iot architecture based on rina," in *2020 23rd Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks and Workshops (ICIN)*, pp. 41–45, IEEE, 2020.
- [6] European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), "Next generation protocols (NGP):An example of a non-IP network protocol architecture based on RINA design principles," standard, 2019.
- [7] J. Day, I. Matta, and K. Mattar, "Networking is IPC: A Guiding Principle to a Better Internet," in *Proceedings of the 2008 ACM CoNEXT Conference*, CoNEXT '08, (New York, NY, USA), Association for Computing Machinery, 2008.
- [8] E. Grasa, B. Gastón, S. van der Meer, M. Crotty, and M. A. Puente, "Simplifying multi-layer network management with RINA," TERENA Networking Conference (TNC), Prague, 2016., 2016.
- [9] S. van der Meer, J. Keeney, L. Fallon, S. Feghhi, and A. de Builélir, "Large-scale experimentation with network abstraction for network configuration management," in *2019 22nd Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks and Workshops (ICIN)*, pp. 60–65, IEEE, 2019.
- [10] E. Grasa, O. Rysavy, O. Lichtner, H. Asgari, J. Day, and L. Chitkushev, "From Protecting protocols to layers: designing, implementing and experimenting with security policies in RINA," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, pp. 1–7, IEEE, 2016.
- [11] I. Amdouni, F. Hrizi, A. Laouiti, E. Grasa, and H. Chaouchi, "Exploring the flexibility of network access control in the recursive internetwork architecture," in *2016 22nd Asia-Pacific Conference on Communications (APCC)*, pp. 559–566, IEEE, 2016.
- [12] S. Vrijders, D. Staessens, D. Colle, F. Salvestrini, E. Grasa, M. Tarzan, and L. Bergesio, "Prototyping the recursive internet architecture: the IRATI project approach," *IEEE Network*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 20–25, 2014.
- [13] V. Maffione, "A light RINA implementation." <https://github.com/rlite/rlite>, 2017.
- [14] Y. Wang, I. Matta, F. Esposito, and J. Day, "Introducing ProtoRINA: a prototype for programming recursive-networking policies," 2014.
- [15] V. Vesely, M. Marek, T. Hykel, and O. Rysavy, "Skip this paper - rinasim: Your recursive internetwork architecture simulator," 2015.
- [16] M. Rizinski, J. Day, and L. Chitkushev, "IoT architecture based on RINA," in *2020 23rd Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks and Workshops (ICIN)*, pp. 41–45, IEEE, 2020.
- [17] T. RamezaniFarkhani and P. Teymooori, "Securing the Internet of Things with recursive InterNetwork architecture (RINA)," in *2018 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC)*, pp. 188–194, IEEE, 2018.
- [18] S. Vrijders, E. Trouva, J. Day, E. Grasa, D. Staessens, D. Colle, M. Pickavet, and L. Chitkushev, "Unreliable inter process communication in ethernet: migrating to rina with the shim dif," in *2013 5th International Congress on Ultra Modern Telecommunications and Control Systems and Workshops (ICUMT)*, pp. 215–221, 2013.
- [19] R. W. Watson, "Timer-based mechanisms in reliable transport protocol connection management," *Computer Networks (1976)*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 47–56, 1981.
- [20] S. Al-Sarawi, M. Anbar, K. Alieyan, and M. Alzubaidi, "Internet of things (iot) communication protocols: Review," in *2017 8th International Conference on Information Technology (ICIT)*, pp. 685–690, 2017.
- [21] "IEEE Standard for an Architectural Framework for the Internet of Things (IoT)," standard, 2020.